

Formation Constants of Ternary Complexes of some Trivalent Metal Ions with 2,2'-Dipyridyl, *o*-Phenanthroline or Histidine as Primary Ligand and Sulphonosalicylidene Anil as Secondary Ligand

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In continuation of our earlier studies¹ on mixed ligand complexes involving Schiff base ligands, we report here the results of pH-metric study of formation of ternary complexes of rare earth metal ions Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III} with 2,2'-dipyridyl (dipy), *o*-phenanthroline (*o*-phen) or histidine (Hist) as primary ligand (A) and sulphonosalicylidene anil (SSAL) as the secondary ligand (L) in aqueous medium at 25° and at a fixed ionic strength (*I*) of 0.1 M (NaClO₄). Irving-Rossotti's pH-titration technique² as modified by others^{3,4} has been followed in order to evaluate the stability constants of the metal-ligand chelates.

Results and Discussion

In the study of M-L system, it has been observed that the n_{11} values, determined by usual procedure², extended over a range $0.24 < n_{11} < 1.94$. This indicated two-step deprotonation of ligand. The proton-ligand stability constant ($\log K_1^{11}$) determined and refined by the usual method² are summarised in Table 1. Here $\log K_1^{11}$ refers to the dissociation of phenolic hydrogen attached to salicylaldehyde moiety and $\log K_2^{11}$ value has been attributed to proton dissociation value of sulphonic acid group⁵. It has been observed from the titration curves (Fig. 1) that the metal-ligand complexation occurred at pH lower than that of metal hydrolysis^{6,7}. The maximum value of n was ~ 0.9 , which suggests 1:1 complexation beyond the region of metal hydrolysis. The plots of n against pL gave metal-ligand formation curves². The metal-ligand stability constants have been evaluated by least-square method² using suitable computer programmings. The stability constant values are given in Table 1. The calculated² standard

TABLE I – PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM AT 25, 35 AND 45° AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AT 25°

I = 0.1 M (NaClO₄)

Cations	Temp. (°C)	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$-\Delta G$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta H$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S$ (cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
H ⁺	25	8.16	4.90			
	35	7.56	4.57			
	45	7.36	4.55			
Pr ^{III}	25	4.75	—	6.47	28.56	74.12
	35	4.30	—			
	45	3.66	—			
Nd ^{III}	25	4.82	—	6.57	25.13	62.28
	35	4.10	—			
	45	3.77	—			
Sm ^{III}	25	4.95	—	6.75	27.42	69.36
	35	4.35	—			
	45	3.90	—			
Gd ^{III}	25	4.78	—	6.51	22.85	51.83
	35	4.30	—			
	45	3.80	—			

deviation (δ) was found to be 0.12 ± 0.04 . It is evident (Table 1) that with decreasing temperature the stability constants showed an increasing trend. This suggests that low temperature is favourable for complexation. The approximate values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying complexation reactions have been determined using standard relations⁸ (Table 1). ΔH is favourable for

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 Fig 1 Titration curves at 25 ($I = 0.1 M NaClO_4$)

complexation as reflected by the negative values in all cases ΔS for the complexes is negative and are not favourable for complexation. However, the negative free energy term suggests that complex formation is a spontaneous one.

The distribution of metal-ligand binary complex species as a function of pH has been determined by using known expressions⁹. From distribution diagram (Fig 2) it has been observed that in all cases rare earth metal ion complex species ML^{2+} and free metal ion M^{3+} change monotonically with pH. The stability constants of the binary complexes of the trivalent rare earth metal ions follow the order $Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} < Sm^{III} > Gd^{III}$. Such difference in the trend of stability constants is not uncommon¹⁰ in the case of lanthanides and this may be traced to be due to varying degree of stabilisation arising out of interaction of f metal orbitals with the ligand field.

An observation of the mixed-ligand system curve shows that in the case of primary complex curve there is a lowering of pH indicating that primary complex formation is complete at $pH \sim 3.5$ since the dissociation

Fig 2 Distribution diagram (M-I)

of primary complex does not take place in the range of dissociation of secondary ligand, it can be considered that the secondary ligand combines with the primary complex just as it does with $[M(aq)_n]^{3+}$ in binary systems. In presence of secondary ligands formation of $[M^{III}(A)(OH)_n]$ is found to be suppressed.

The relative order of stability of ternary complexes in terms of metal ion is $Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} < Sm^{III} > Gd^{III}$ which may be due to the increasing ionic radius and increasing charge/radius ratio of the rare earths. In case of histidine, there is some reversal in order of the stability constant for Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} . Such order is however not uncommon in the case of lanthanides for reasons as mentioned earlier¹⁰. In all cases the stability of mixed ligand complexes is found to be less than the corresponding binary complexes. This is evident from negative $\Delta \log K (= \log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{MI}^M)$ values (Table 2). Here the primary ligand molecules like dipyrindyl or *o*-phenanthroline may put a barrier to the approach of the secondary Schiff base ligand and this might lead to a decrease in the stability of the ternary complexes.

Experimental

The Schiff base ligand *p*-sulphosalicylidene anil (SSAL) was prepared by following the reported method¹¹. The purity of the sample was checked by elemental analysis. All other chemicals were either of A.R. grade or purified before use. The rare earth metals were estimated by EDTA method¹². The metal perchlorates were dissolved in $0.1 M HClO_4$ to avoid metal

TABLE 2 — STABILITY CONSTANTS OF TERNARY (M-A-L) SYSTEM IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM

Temp. 25°, I = 0.1 M (NaClO₄)

System	Stability constant	$\Delta \log K^*$
$\log K_{Pr-bipy-L}^{Pr-bipy}$	3.71	-1.04
$\log K_{Nd-bipy-L}^{Nd-bipy}$	4.17	-0.65
$\log K_{Sm-bipy-L}^{Sm-bipy}$	4.60	-0.35
$\log K_{Gd-bipy-L}^{Gd-bipy}$	4.62	-0.16
$\log K_{Pr-o-phen-L}^{Pr-o-phen}$	3.63	-1.12
$\log K_{Nd-o-phen-L}^{Nd-o-phen}$	3.93	-0.89
$\log K_{Sm-o-phen-L}^{Sm-o-phen}$	4.50	-0.45
$\log K_{Gd-o-phen-L}^{Gd-o-phen}$	4.58	-0.20
$\log K_{Pr-Hist-L}^{Pr-Hist}$	3.82	-0.93
$\log K_{Nd-Hist-L}^{Nd-Hist}$	3.50	-1.32
$\log K_{Sm-Hist-L}^{Sm-Hist}$	3.80	-0.98
$\log K_{Gd-Hist-L}^{Gd-Hist}$	3.53	-1.25

$$^* \Delta \log K = \log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M$$

hydrolysis. Procedure for pH-metric titrations for the study of the binary complexes is the same as reported earlier⁵. For the pH-metric study of ternary complexation, the following solutions were used for titration against standard sodium hydroxide (0.39 M): (A) $2 \times 10^{-2} M HClO_4$ (acid curve), (B) $2 \times 10^{-2} M HClO_4 + 2 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand solution (secondary ligand curve), (C) $2 \times 10^{-2} M HClO_4 + 2 \times 10^{-3} M$ primary ligand + $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal solution (primary complex curve) and (D) $2 \times 10^{-2} M HClO_4 + 2 \times 10^{-3} M$ primary ligand + $2 \times 10^{-3} M$

metal solution + $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand solution (mixed ligand complex curve). In each case the total volume was made up to 50 ml and ionic strength maintained at 0.1 M by addition of appropriate amount of neutral NaClO₄ solution. The ratio between metal, primary ligand and secondary ligand was kept at 1 : 1 : 1. All titrations were carried out at 25°. A representative titration curve for the Sm-bipy-SSAL system has been shown in Fig. 1.

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